

Hydronyms are a component of onomastics

Gulnoza Qurbonova Abduholiq qizi

Termez Pedagogical Institute. Surkhandarya. Uzbekistan

The teacher of the department "Foreign languages theory and methodology"

e-mail: gulnozaqurbonova@gmail.com

Annotation: This article is about the English hydronyms, its origins, characteristics and types. The geographical names of the British Isles are quite well studied. These islands represent an area with clearly defined natural boundaries. The names that developed in England and the UK as a whole have become widespread in other countries where English is spoken.

Key words: hydronyms, toponyms, geographical names, linguistics, types structure.

Since time immemorial, people have named rivers, lakes, and springs in the area where they live, as well as each lake and each spring in order to distinguish them from each other. For example: Amudarya, Amazon, Syrdarya, Thames, Surkhandarya, Zarafshan, Nile, Oykol, Lake Baikal, Tashbulok, Kotyrbulok, Marjanbulok, Zirabulok. It can be seen from this that nouns with adjectives arise due to the need to name things and events, objects individually. According to the linguist B. Yoldoshev, "The crown jewel of human thought is its ability to generalize. If there was no such ability to generalize, any language would become a super-complex and incomprehensible phenomenon consisting of millions, billions of words and grammatical devices. Therefore, naming things and events individually and individually with proper nouns is considered a necessary necessity and the result of legality. In fact, as language performs a social function in society, it should reveal the worldview and thinking of people belonging to this society. European linguists approach the analysis of the social nature of language through the sociolinguistic principle. "The main field that analyzes the social nature of language is sociolinguistics. It follows a number of criteria, such as historicity, vitality, normativeness, and territoriality, in illuminating the social nature of the language. Of course, it can be understood that the analysis of onomastic units, especially hydronyms, factors such as historicity, vitality, normativity, territoriality become important in the process of scientific study. Language as a social phenomenon is distinguished from natural phenomena. For example, the natural biological and

physiological characteristics of people (eating, breathing, development, etc.) develop in accordance with the laws of nature, independently of society. But in order to speak and think in a language, it is necessary to have a personal society (social environment). Because language arose as a result of the needs of people to communicate with each other and exchange ideas. That is why language, unlike natural phenomena, is a social phenomenon created and served by human society.

In world linguistics, onomastics has its own historical development, which can be conditionally divided into the following stages:

I stage: the period of registration and comparison of onomastic units, including the period up to the 19th century, considered to be the period that developed in harmony with the period of comparative-historical linguistics;

II stage: the period of formation of onomastics as a science, covering the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century. The roots of this science appeared in European and Russian linguistics in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. A.H. Vosgokov, A.I. In the works of scientists such as Sobolevsky, A. A. Shakhmatov, M. Fasmer, S. K. Kuznetsov, P. L. Mashtakova, preliminary information about the collection and analysis of onomastic material in the Russian language was presented;

III stage: the scientific-theoretical or purely onomastic period, which includes the system-structural period and anthropocentric periods of linguistics. This period includes the period from the 20s of the 20th century to the present day. During this period, onomastic material was collected separately, like lexical, phonetic, morphological and other level units of the language, and researched in different directions;

The stages of development of toponymy as a special field are determined by long historical processes. Also, the study from the point of view of different disciplines, the study on the basis of interdisciplinary integration determines how important this field is. is studied. In the science of history, the study of historical toponymy is a very broad object of study, and there are opinions that it was born from the combination of different disciplines. These considerations determine how important the field is.

It is known from the history of linguistics that with the emergence of views on analogy and anamalia, onomasiological (Yun oyonacia-atash, naming + ovog - word, speech- the science of names is the branch of linguistics that studies the naming of

various objects) processes attracted researchers. It is not a secret that has been interesting. As people formed ideas about the environment, they tried to give names to everything in nature as a result of these ideas. It can be seen that this movement was especially noticeable during the philosophical period of Greek linguistics. In the philosophical period of linguistics, Heraclitus and his supporters put forward the following idea when solving the problem of the relationship between a word and an object. "They are in an inseparable connection with the object, the thing that each name signifies, and the essence of the objects is revealed and "opened" in the names.

More precisely, they put forward the idea that each name reflects the nature and essence of the object it represents, just like trees in water and ourselves in a mirror. More precisely, the connection between the subject and the words representing them is given by nature, and this connection is a natural, necessary connection. It is not for nothing that these issues have attracted the attention of linguists for a long time. Because Plato, one of the representatives of the philosophical period of Greek linguistics, in his famous work called "Cratylus", specifically focused on the issue of the relationship between the subject and its name, which was the most urgent problem in the linguistics of that time, can be a proof of our opinion. Various features of nouns in the language were given detailed information in the works written by Aristotle, Plato, Heraclitus, and Demosthenes. For example, in "Poetics", Aristotle's famous work on the development of such sciences as linguistics, literary studies, and philosophy, while thinking about eloquence, he describes a noun as "a noun is complex, meaningful, does not indicate time, its parts do not exist by themselves. "no" is a word that does not mean ". describes as

The linguist scientist B. Yoldoshev said that "in the European renaissance period and subsequent centuries, researchers such as T. Hobbs, J. Locke, G. Leibniz, J. Mill, H. Joseph in linguistics "famous nouns, their language vocabulary expressed opinions on the issue of the place in the Avy layer" These opinions were empirical in nature and mainly consisted of discussions. Naming and naming issues have attracted not only linguists, but also logicians and philosophers. John Stuart Mill (1806-1873), an English logician who lived and worked in the 19th century, spent a lot of effort. According to his interpretation, proper nouns do not convey meaning, they help to know an object and distinguish it from other objects as unique signs and labels. The name of an object or person (noun) cannot be a full basis for the description of that object or person. Developing his thoughts, J. Mill divides words into two groups: a) words-symbols, b) characterizing (connotative) words. Connotative words are

formed after proper nouns. This idea was important from the point of view of its time.

English linguist Alan Gardiner's "Theory of Famous Names" (1954) took the science of onomastics to a new level. Developing D. Mill's opinion about the lack of meaning in nouns, A. Gardiner states that nouns are unique names that express a set of clear, concrete ideas about an object, an event. From a historical point of view, figurative nouns came into being earlier, earlier.

Used literature:

1. Abduholiqovna Q. G. PRELIMINARY STUDY OF UZBEK HYDRONYMY ON THE ROOTS. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*. – 2021.
2. <https://scholar.google.com/scholar?oi=bibs&cluster=9493385005150413450&btnI=1&hl=ru>
3. Qurbonova Gulnoza Abdukhalik qizi. № 17 (255) / 2019 The notions of “knowledge”, “action” and “learning” p217 *Молодой ученый Международный научный журнал*
4. Qurbonova gulnoza abduholiqovna. (2021). Epistemological approaches and the psychology of knowledge. *Emergent: journal of educational discoveries and lifelong learning (ejedl)*, 2(04), 50–53. Retrieved from <https://ejedl.academiascience.org/index.php/ejedl/article/view/23>
5. Qurbonova gulnoza abduholiqovna. (2021). Development of the concept “knowledge” in english. *Academicia globe: inderscience research*, 2(04), 91–94. Retrieved from <https://agir.academiascience.org/index.php/agir/article/view/59>
6. Qurbonova gulnoza abduholiqovna, & toshtemirova dinora qurbonazarovna. (2021). Difficulties of learning english. *Journalnx - a multidisciplinary peer reviewed journal*, 7(10), 128–131. <https://doi.org/10.17605/osf.io/hqx67>
7. Abduholiqovna q. G. Preliminary study of uzbek hydronymy on the roots // *academicia: an international multidisciplinary research journal*. – 2021. – т. 11. – №. 7. – с. 215-218.
8. Khudayberdievich m.m. (2023). The concepts of text and discourse in linguistics. *Journal of advanced linguistic studies*.
9. https://bahripublications.co.in/pdf/jals%2c%20vol.%2010%2c%20no.%20%2c%20jun-dec%202023/38%20-%20the%20study%20of%20hydronymy%20-%20fully%20final.pdf?_t=1702980029